

Quantum Free Particle $\exp(ipx)$ With p Being Dynamic and x Static Part IV: Coupled Maximization of Shannon's Entropy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 6, 2024

In this note, we consider $P(x)=1/L$ and $\exp(ipx)$ from the point of maximization of Shannon's entropy. In this view, x is a static variable a priori. We note that maximization of Shannon's entropy is done subject to a priori constraints. For example, a $P(x)$ solution will have an average x value, but unless this is imposed a priori, we argue that it should not appear in a constraint expression. In such a case, there is no constraint for placing a particle at rest at some x in a range L . Maximization of Shannon's probability with no constraint yields $P(x)=\text{constant}$. Given that one may position a rest mass, there is no net momentum, so one may consider $P(x)=P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x)$, as we have argued in Parts I,II and III. For example, the rest mass may be a very small box with two photons, one moving with p and the other with $-p$.

The question then becomes: What is $P_d(p,x)$ from the point of view of entropy maximization? We argued in previous parts that one must have probability flow in x because there is p (energy flux). This flow, however, is special in the sense that it does have an a priori constraint on x , namely that one average $\int dx x P_d(p,x) = 0$ because otherwise there would be biased flow in x . Non-biased flow in x , however, is consistent with maximum entropy for $P(x)$. Thus, it seems that $P_d(p,x)$ should also be associated with maximization of Shannon's entropy (i.e. coupled maximization through an x average constraint). A similar maximization holds for $-p$, but with a different Lagrange multiplier. For the $P(x)$ maximization to be consistent with that of $P_d(p,x)$ and $P_d(-p,x)$ separately, Lagrange multipliers must have the same magnitude, but opposite signs.

Thus, we argue that one may maximize entropy for both $P(x)$ and $P_d(p,x)$ and $P_d(-p,x)$ separately. The result for $P_d(p,x)$ is consistent with $\exp(ipx)$ (if one chooses ip as the Lagrange multiplier for $P_d(p,x)$). We try to give arguments for this. The overall result seems to follow from both the maximization of $P(x)$ and $P_d(p,x)$'s, not one from one alone. In other words, it seems as if there is coupled maximization of Shannon's entropy.

$P(x)=1/L$ and Maximization of Shannon's Entropy

In Parts I,II, III, we belaboured the point that $P(x)=1/L$ applies to a static object that may be distributed to different x points. This is a typical classical probability problem with no dynamics. In such a case one maximizes Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint. We argue that there is no constraint. If the interval is centered about $x=0$, one might argue that by symmetry x (average) = 0, but this is not an a priori constraint, but anticipates the maximization of Shannon's entropy. Thus, there is no constraint and one maximizes:

$$-P(x) \ln(P(x)) \longrightarrow \ln(P(x)) = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad P(x) = \text{constant} \quad ((1))$$

In other words, no x point is favoured and so there is no bias in x .

If one distributes a static particle in x , this means that it has energy, but no net momentum. This does not mean, however, that a tiny box with two photons moving with p and $-p$ is disallowed. It

has the appearance of a particle with no net momentum, but with energy, but in fact there is p and $-p$. Thus, we suggest (as in Parts I,II, III) that:

$$P(x) = P_d(p,x) P_d(-p,x) \quad ((2))$$

We further suggest that $P_d(p,x)$ is a dynamic sort of probability which involves probability flow in space, but must respect the idea of maximum Shannon's entropy imposed by ((1)). One may see that given that $P(x)=\text{constant}$, p and $-p$ must cancel through addition, i.e. $P_d(p,x) = \text{a power}(p)$ with x appearing in some manner.

Maximization of Shannon's Entropy and $P_d(p,x)$

One might wonder if $P_d(p,x)$ follows from maximizing Shannon's entropy. One may note that the concept of $P_d(p,x)$ follows from $P(x)$ which is already subject to maximization of Shannon's entropy. Thus, $P_d(p,x)$ is constrained to respect ((1)). It is not completely arbitrary. At the same time there seems to be biased motion in x in one direction. This implies that x must appear and one cannot have the same probability at each x . The best possible solution compatible with $P(x)=\text{constant}$ is one which has no bias in x on average, i.e. $x \text{ average} = 0$. In such a case, there is an a priori constraint on x average and this constraint is imposed so that $P_d(p,x)$ respects the ((1)), the maximization of Shannon's entropy for $P(x)$.

One may suggest that one consider Shannon entropy maximization of $P_d(p,x)$ with the constraint that $\int dx \ x P_d(p,x) = 0$ (and the same for $P_d(-p,x)$). This leads to two expressions to maximize, with different Lagrange multipliers, i.e.

$$P_d(p,x) \ln(P_d(p,x)) + b_1 x P_d(p,x) \quad ((3a)) \text{ and } P_d(-p,x) \ln(P_d(-p,x)) + b_2 x P_d(-p,x) \quad ((3b))$$

One may multiply ((3a)) by $P_d(-p,x)$ and ((3b)) by $P_d(p,x)$. Then one should maximize:

$$P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x) \ln\{ P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x) \} + (b_1+b_2) x P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x) \quad ((4))$$

$$((4)), \text{ however, must be consistent with } ((1)), \text{ so: } b_1+b_2 = 0 \quad ((5))$$

Thus, separate Shannon's entropy maximization seems to apply to $P_d(p,x)$ and $P_d(-p,x)$, but with constraints which respect ((1)).

$$\text{Maximization of } ((3a)) \text{ leads to: } P_d(p,x) = \exp(b_1 x) \text{ and } P_d(-p,x) = \exp(b_2 x) \text{ with } ((5))$$

There are two issues with ((5)). First, $P_d(p,x)$ grows (or decreases) indefinitely in x . It would be better for it to be periodic so $b_1 = i |b_1|$. Secondly, b_1 should be an odd function of p , it seems. In fact, the momentum flow is due to the p , energy flux and it seems that $b_1=p$. It does not seem that there is extra information in the form of a new odd function of p .

One may ask, however: What are the consequences of using $\exp(ipx)$?

One may see that:

$$\int dx \exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = 0 \text{ unless } p_1=p_2. \quad ((6))$$

In other words, the choice of $b_1=p$ leads to the notion of momentum conservation. Thus, it seems reasonable to use $\exp(ipx)$.

As a result, it seems that one may use maximization of Shannon's entropy for a dynamic probability $P_d(p,x)$, but this maximization is not independent of the maximization of Shannon's entropy for $P(x)=P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x)$. $P(x)$ has an average x of 0 if L has $x=0$ as its center and this notion of x average is imposed a priori on $P_d(p,x)$ to make it consistent with $P(x)=1/L$. Furthermore, the Lagrange multiplier may be chosen to be ip , where the choice of p is ultimately linked to $P(x)=P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x)$. It seems that a coupled maximization of $P_d(p,x)$ and $P_d(-p,x)$ separately, in conjunction with a maximization of Shannon's entropy for $P(x)=P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x)$ is performed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $P(x)=1/L$ represents a typical classical probability problem which has nothing to do with dynamics, but with the placement of a rest mass at different x points. One may maximize $-P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to no a priori constraint to find that $P(x)=\text{constant}$. Given that one places a particle at each x point, this particle may be thought of as a composite p and $-p$ at each x , or $P(x) = P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x)$.

We ask: Is it possible to solve for $P_d(p,x)$ using maximization of Shannon's entropy? In such a case, $P_d(p,x)$ contains x because it involves probability flow in the direction of p . If so, one must respect the maximization of $P(x)$. Given that probability is not constant in x , the next best thing is to have x average $=0$, which also holds for $P(x)$ (with L centered about $x=0$). Thus, we argue that one seems to have coupled maximization of Shannon's entropy. If one writes maximization of Shannon's entropy for $P_d(p,x)$ and $P_d(-p,x)$ with the x -average $=0$ a priori constraint, due to $P(x)=1/L$, but with different Lagrange multipliers, one finds that one Lagrange multiplier is the negative of the other for the two $P_d(p,x)$, $P_d(-p,x)$ to be compatible with $P(x)$ entropy maximization. We go one step further and identify the Lagrange multiplier of $P_d(p,x)$ as ip . "1" is chosen to have a periodic probability, which neither grows or declines indefinitely in x . In such a case, if one shifts the origin to the center of $\sin(px)$, then x average is 0 in each wavelength, i.e. there is periodic motion with symmetrical crests and troughs.